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An Analysis of the Impact of the 2008 Global Financial Crisis on Health Expenditures in Türkiye: Evidence from 1999–2012¹

2008 Küresel FinansalKrizinin Türkiye'deki Sağlık Harcamaları Üzerindeki Etkisinin Analizi: 1999-2012 Yılları Arasındaki Kanıtlar

ABSTRACT

Crises that have occurred on a global scale in the past have influenced the world economy in various ways. Among these, one of the most significant crises affecting the global economy was the 2008 Global Financial Crisis, which originated in the United States in 2007 and manifested its impact in 2008. This crisis profoundly affected many countries, and numerous sectors were influenced by it. It is assumed that the health sector is among the sectors impacted by global crises. Considering that the health sector encompasses activities related to the well-being of citizens and provides various services to them, it can be argued that disruptions or deficiencies in this sector may affect human capital in a country, thereby producing broader economic implications. For this reason, the present study aims to determine the effects of the 2008 Global Financial Crisis on health expenditures in Türkiye. For this purpose, health expenditures and developments in the field of healthcare in Türkiye were examined for the period between 1999 and 2012. This period was selected in order to enable a comparison of health-related data in the years preceding the crisis with those following it. The study presents the changes in health expenditures in Türkiye through various indicators. The findings reveal that during this period, health investments increased, the total number of healthcare institutions expanded, and overall health expenditures continuously rose (except in 2009). Furthermore, the share of total health expenditure in GDP increased until 2008, after which it declined. Based on the GDP ratio, it can be inferred that the global financial crisis adversely affected human capital. Nevertheless, despite the crisis, the analysis indicates that many health indicators in Türkiye continued to exhibit upward trends.

Keywords: Crisis, 2008 global financial crisis, health expenditures.

ÖZET

Geçmişte meydana gelen küresel ölçekteki krizler dünya ekonomisini çeşitli yönleriyle etkilemiştir. Dünya ekonomisini önemli ölçüde etkileyen küresel ölçekte meydana gelen krizlerden biri, Amerika Birleşik Devletleri merkezli 2007 yılında başlayan ve etkisini 2008 yılında gösteren 2008 küresel finansal krizdir. Söz konusu kriz birçok ülkeyi derinden etkilemiştir. Birçok sektör bu durumdan etkilenmiştir. Küresel krizlerden etkilenen sektörlerden birinin sağlık sektörü olduğu düşünülmektedir. Sağlık sektörüne bir ülkede yaşayan vatandaşların sağlığı ile ilgili çalışmaların yapıldığı, vatandaşlara çeşitli imkânların sunulduğu bir sektör olarak bakıldığında bu sektörde meydana gelen bozulmalar veya yetersizlikler ülkedeki beşeri sermayeyi etkileyeceği ve bu durumun ekonomi üzerinde etkileri olacağı söylenebilir. Bu nedenle çalışmada 2008 küresel finansal krizin Türkiye'de sağlık harcamaları üzerindeki etkilerinin belirlenmesi amaçlanmıştır. Bu amaçla Türkiye'de sağlık alanında yapılan harcamalar ve bu alanda meydana gelen gelişmeler 1999 ile 2012 yılları arasındaki dönem dikkate alınarak incelenmiştir. Bu dönemin seçilme nedeni 2008 küresel finansal krizinden önceki yıllar ile kriz meydana geldikten sonraki yıllarda sağlık alanındaki verilerin karşılaştırılabilmesinin sağlanmasıdır. Çalışmada Türkiye'deki sağlık harcamalarında meydana gelen değişimler çeşitli göstergeler yardımıyla sunulmuştur. Bulgular bu dönemde Türkiye'de sağlık yatırımlarının arttığını, toplam sağlık kurum sayısının arttığını, toplam sağlık harcamalarının sürekli arttığını (2009 yılı hariç), toplam sağlık harcamasının GSYİH oranının 2008 yılına kadar arttığını ondan sonra düştüğünü göstermektedir. GSYİH oranından yola çıkarak küresel finansal krizin beşeri sermayeyi olumsuz etkilediği söylenebilir. Ayrıca yaşanan küresel finansal krize rağmen Türkiye'de sağlık alanındaki birçok göstergedeki okların yukarı doğru artış gösterdiği sonucuna ulaşılmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Kriz, 2008 küresel finansal kriz, sağlık harcamaları.

¹ This study is derived from the master's thesis titled "The Effects of the Global Financial Crisis on Health Expenditures: The Case of Türkiye", prepared in the Department of Economics at the Institute of Social Sciences, Nevşehir Hacı Bektaş Veli University.

1. INTRODUCTION

The economic development of countries can be demonstrated through various indicators. The Human Development Index (HDI), developed by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), may be used as an indicator of economic development. The HDI is based on three variables, which are considered to represent a wide range of factors associated with economic development. As an educational criterion, it includes the adult literacy rate and school enrollment ratio; as a welfare criterion, the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita adjusted for Purchasing Power Parity (PPP); and as a health criterion, which is also a health outcome, life expectancy at birth. Thus, since health constitutes one of the three essential dimensions of the HDI, understanding the relationship between health and economic development is of great importance. This concept has gained further significance with the prominence of the notion of human capital and the increasing share of health expenditures within countries' total expenditures (Tüylüoğlu & Tekin, 2009).

Economic growth theories have emphasized the issue of human capital by attributing economic growth to endogenous factors. Therefore, the development of human capital is a crucial matter for any country. The enhancement and improvement of human capital levels depend on advancements in health and education. Expenditures directed toward education and healthcare improve the level of human capital, which, in turn, positively influences economic growth through increased productivity (Ay, Kızılkaya, & Koçak, 2013). The presence of healthy individuals in a society signifies qualified human resources, which are vital for development. In this regard, per capita health expenditures made by governments are considered one of the indicators of development (Karagöz & Tetik, 2009).

In today's globalized world, the relationship between health and the economy has increasingly become a significant subject discussed among economists and policymakers. In explaining this relationship, two aspects are examined for developed and developing countries. Globally accepted health indicators that explain the relationship between health and growth include infant and child mortality rates and crude death rates, while the most common economic indicators include GDP, GDP per capita, and health expenditures (Tıraşoğlu & Yıldırım, 2012). The health sector refers to the systems and subsystems established in various fields that produce, consume, supply, and demand every kind of good and service with direct, indirect, or primary effects on health, encompassing statuses, products, individuals, institutions, and organizations (Sargutan, 2005). For the preparation of significant strategic plans and their implementation, it is essential for a country to be aware of factors such as education, level of economic development, health indicators, health status, and the quantitative structure of its population both at present and in the future. Based on the changing demographic structure, health problems, infrastructure, and service needs are identified, and plans are developed accordingly (Akın & Ersoy, 2012).

In this study, the period between 1999 and 2012 was taken as the basis to determine the impact of the 2008 Global Financial Crisis on health expenditures in Türkiye. Accordingly, changes in health expenditures and developments in the field of health in Türkiye during these years were analyzed through various demographic and economic indicators.

2. HEALTH EXPENDITURES IN TÜRKİYE

Expenditures made for the protection and improvement of health are referred to as health expenditures. Investments in the health sector promote technological progress, which in turn stimulates growth and subsequently leads to further increases in health expenditures. Health expenditures contribute to prolonging human life expectancy and enhancing quality of life. In today's world, governments are increasingly attaching importance to health expenditures. As a key factor in economic growth and development, health expenditures vary depending on the level of development of countries. The share allocated to health expenditures in developed countries is higher compared to developing countries. In countries that adopt the social state model, greater budgetary resources are allocated to fundamental public services such as education and healthcare (Akar, 2014).

In recent years, health expenditures have shown an increase in both total income and total spending. The main reasons for the growth in health expenditures can be listed as follows (Kılavuz, 2010):

- The labor-intensive nature of the sector,
- Supply-induced demand,
- Rising demand for health expenditures with increasing income,
- Increased prevalence of chronic diseases and disabilities due to longer life expectancy,
- Growing health awareness,

- Rising costs resulting from asymmetric information,
- The use of high-capital advanced technology in the health sector.

Table 1. Health Sector Investments in Türkiye (1993–2002 and 2003–2012)

Health Facility	1993-2002	2003-2012
Hospital and New Building	311	606
Primary Healthcare Facility	767	1.508
Total	1.078	2.114

Source: Presentation of the 2013 Fiscal Year Budget of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Türkiye to the Planning and Budget Committee of the Grand National Assembly of Türkiye

Between 1993 and 2002, the number of hospitals and newly constructed buildings was 311, whereas in the period between 2003 and 2012 this figure rose to 606, nearly doubling. Similarly, the number of primary healthcare facilities increased from 767 in the years 1993–2002 to 1,508 during the years 2003–2012, which coincides with the implementation of the Health Transformation Program.

3. DEVELOPMENTS IN THE HEALTH SECTOR WITHIN THE TÜRKİYE ECONOMY

Health is one of the most important factors determining the living standards of both society and individuals. Developments in healthcare not only provide personal economic benefits but also contribute to the overall development of a country. The impact of health on economic growth and development has become a popular subject of interest among researchers. In most studies, improvements in the healthcare sector have been shown to generate positive outcomes for economic growth. However, the extent of these effects differs from country to country (Çalışkan, Karabacak, & Meçik, 2013).

Developments in the field of health economics can also be illustrated through graphical representations. Figure 1 presents a graph showing the number of healthcare institutions in Türkiye between 1999 and 2012. While the total number of healthcare institutions was 1,174 in 1999, this figure rose to 29,960 by 2012. During the 2008 crisis, the number of healthcare institutions was 13,818, which increased to 15,205 in 2009. Thus, even during the crisis period, the total number of healthcare institutions continued to rise.

Figure 1. The Number of Healthcare Institutions in Türkiye (1999–2012) **Source:** Türkiye Statistical Institute, Health Statistics 1999–2012

In 1999, the total number of hospital beds was 153,464, whereas by 2012 this figure had increased to 200,072. In 2000, a decline was observed compared to 1999. While the total number of beds was 183,183 in 2008, it rose to 188,638 in 2009. In 2010, the number of beds reached 200,239, but it decreased to 194,504 in 2011. Apart from these fluctuations, the overall trend indicates an increase in the total number of beds (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The Total Number of Hospital Beds in Türkiye (1999–2012) **Source:** Türkiye Statistical Institute, Health Statistics 1999–2012

Figure 3. Population per Physician in Türkiye (1999–2012) **Source:** Türkiye Statistical Institute, Health Statistics 1999–2012

In 1999, the number of persons per physician was 773, whereas by 2012 this figure had declined to 583. Developments in the healthcare sector, particularly the increase in the number of physicians, have reduced the number of persons per physician. As shown in Figure 3, the downward trend in the number of persons per physician continued even during the 2008 crisis period.

Figure 4. Population per Health Officer in Türkiye (1999–2012) **Source:** Türkiye Statistical Institute, Health Statistics 1999–2012

As shown in Figure 4, with the increase in the number of health officers, the number of persons per health officer has declined. In 1999, the number of persons per health officer was 1,472; by 2008, this figure had decreased to 794, and by 2012, it had further dropped to 617.

4. THE IMPACT OF THE 2008 GLOBAL FINANCIAL CRISIS ON HEALTH EXPENDITURES IN TÜRKİYE

The human capital theory, developed in the mid-20th century by Gary Becker and colleagues, identified education and health as its two fundamental pillars. According to this theory, human capital plays a significant role in explaining differences in national income levels and variations in economic growth. This perspective has long been accepted among economists. Historically, its origins can even be traced back to the works of Adam Smith and Alfred Marshall (Çetin & Ecevit, 2010).

Since the 1960s, the health sector has emerged as a crucial field in which countries across the world have carried out intensive efforts. Numerous reforms and new practices have been introduced to improve healthcare systems. In an increasingly globalized world, health indicators are considered essential determinants of development levels and indicators of growth. Therefore, healthcare services must be enhanced and expanded at both national and international levels (Ersöz, 2008).

A crisis can be defined as a period of decline in a country or economy triggered by a financial breakdown. In such cases, the country typically experiences a reduction in liquidity, a decline in income levels, changes in prices (either increases or decreases) due to deflation or inflation, a rise in unemployment rates, and a contraction in both investment and trade volumes. Owing to globalization, the impacts of crises today can be widespread and far-reaching (Karadağ Çaman & Çilingiroğlu, 2009).

One of the areas directly and indirectly affected by crises, which have economic and social repercussions on societies, is the healthcare sector. Crises may indirectly affect health through factors such as hygiene, nutrition, and shelter, while directly influencing health expenditures or investments by reducing the resources allocated to healthcare. The consequences of crises for health may sometimes manifest as higher mortality rates and increased incidence of infant and childhood diseases, and at other times as reductions in health budgets and expenditures. It is important to note, however, that these two aspects are not independent of one another (Memişoğlu & Durgun, 2011).

In developing countries, factors such as unemployment, the informal economy, inflation, and fluctuations in income distribution contribute to rising health expenditures. In developed countries, on the other hand, declining birth rates, increasing life expectancy, and the growing elderly population are the main drivers of rising health expenditures (Gökbunar & Koç, 2009).

Figure 5. Total Health Expenditures in Türkiye (Million TL), 1999–2012 **Source:** Türkiye Statistical Institute, Health Statistics 1999–2012

With the rapid growth of the Turkish economy, an increase in health expenditures has also been observed. In 1999, health expenditures amounted to 4,985 million TL, rising to 50,904 million TL in 2007. In 2008, health expenditures in Türkiye reached 57,740 million TL and further increased to 76,358 million TL by 2012. While total health expenditures were 57,740 million TL in 2008, they rose to 57,911 million TL in 2009. As illustrated in Figure 5, health expenditures in Türkiye continued to increase despite the global crisis that began in mid-2007. However, it is necessary to consider whether public expenditures increased in real terms during crisis periods. Notably, significant increases in health expenditures were observed with the implementation of the Health Transformation Program in 2002.

In 1999, total health expenditures amounted to 4,985 million TL, representing 4.8% of GDP. By 2007, total health expenditures had increased to 50,904 million TL, accounting for 6.0% of GDP (Figure 6). Although health expenditures continued to increase after 2008, their share in GDP did not show substantial variation. While health expenditures appeared to rise, their share within GDP actually declined. In 2008 and 2009, the share of total health expenditures in GDP rose to 6.1%; however, in 2010 it fell to 5.6%, declined further to 5.3% in 2011, and then slightly increased to 5.4% in 2012 (Figure 6). Overall, it can be concluded that the 2008 Global Financial Crisis coincided with an increase in health expenditures in Türkiye.

Figure 6. Ratio of Total Health Expenditures to GDP (%), 1999–2012 **Source:** Türkiye Statistical Institute, Health Statistics 1999–2012

In Türkiye, the share of total health expenditures in GDP increased between 2005 and 2008. However, in 2008–2009 the share remained stable. This situation can be attributed to the Global Financial Crisis of 2008; although total health expenditures rose, there was in fact a real decline in health spending. It may therefore be argued that the global crisis had an adverse effect on human capital (Figure 6).

Private health expenditures hold a significant share in treatment services and outpatient diagnostics. During this period, the inclusion of insured individuals covered by the social security fund in private healthcare services positively contributed to the development of the private healthcare sector. Private health institutions also began to provide services to individuals under the public social security system, through package-based services and invoicing based on an open billing system (Yurdadoğ, 2007, p. 607).

Figure 7: Share of Public and Private Health Expenditures in GDP (%), 1999–2012 **Source:** Türkiye Statistical Institute, Health Statistics 1999–2012

In the figure above, the red color represents the private sector, while the blue color indicates the public sector. In 1999, the share of public health expenditures in GDP was 2.91%, which increased to 4.14% by 2012. In contrast, the share of private health expenditures in GDP decreased from 1.85% in 1999 to 1.25% in 2012 (Figure 7).

5. CONCLUSION

With the advancements in the information sector and technological progress, healthcare expenditures have increased. However, the Global Financial Crisis of 2008 led to a slowdown in the growth rates of countries, and the disproportion between the rise in health expenditures and the decline in growth rates created pressure on national budgets. The crisis negatively affected essential elements of health such as sanitation, nutrition, and shelter, while also reducing the capital allocated to the healthcare sector.

In this study, graphical indicators are presented for total health expenditures and their share of GDP in Türkiye between 1999 and 2012. In 2008, total health expenditures amounted to 57,740 million TL, rising slightly to 57,911 million TL in 2009. Although there was an increase in total health expenditures, their share in GDP remained constant at 6.1% in both 2008 and 2009, indicating that no real growth occurred. In 2010, while total health expenditures rose to 61,678 million TL, their share of GDP decreased to 5.3%. In 2011, health expenditures reached 68,607 million TL and further increased to 76,358 million TL in 2012. Nevertheless, the share of health expenditures in GDP declined from 5.6% to 5.4%.

When considering health expenditures and health-related indicators, the share of public health expenditures in GDP increased from 2.91% in 1999 to 4.14% in 2012, showing a rise of 1.23 percentage points. By contrast, the share of private health expenditures in GDP decreased from 1.85% in 1999 to 1.25% in 2012, reflecting a decline of 0.6 percentage points.

Economic factors can produce both positive and negative outcomes on healthcare services and health expenditures. Economic crises and financial bottlenecks tend to adversely affect the healthcare sector. Crises negatively influence developing countries where human capital, employment levels, infrastructure, educational services, and healthcare services cannot sufficiently reach all segments of society. Therefore, the causes of crises should be examined, and permanent measures aimed at enhancing the socioeconomic welfare of society should be introduced by regulatory and supervisory institutions, governments, policymakers, and academics.

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